

PATHOLOGICAL COURSE OF PREGNANCY AND LABOR IN WOMEN WITH ADENOMYOSIS

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Relevance. Over the past few years, a new direction in reproductive medicine has been the study of the link between adenomyosis and adverse pregnancy outcomes. According to expert reports, the incidence of adenomyosis in the active reproductive age in our country, Kazakhstan, and Ukraine is 15-17%, and slightly lower in Belarus at 10%. A similar incidence is observed in other developed countries. Recent studies have shown that adenomyosis not only impacts infertility but is also associated with a number of obstetric complications after successful conception.

Objective of the study: To study the course of pregnancy, labor, and the postpartum period in women with adenomyosis.

Material and methods of research: A retrospective analysis of labor histories and outpatient records of 203 women registered at the Republican Perinatal Center (RPC) from 2019 to 2021 was conducted. According to outpatient records, clinical, and ultrasound data, 30 (14.8%) women suffered from adenomyosis, while hysteroscopic criteria were identified in 37 (18.2%) patients. Depending on the presence of adenomyosis, two groups were formed: the study group (n=37) consisted of pregnant women with grade 1 and 2 adenomyosis, and the control group (n=166) included conditionally healthy pregnant women without adenomyosis (selected via random sampling).

Research results. According to the data of this study, in pregnant patients with grade 1 and 2 adenomyosis, the number of early reproductive losses and preterm labor significantly increases ($p<0.05$). During pregnancy, placental dysfunction with hemodynamic disturbances and fetal growth restriction (FGR) forms statistically significantly more frequently ($p<0.05$). The incidence of hypertensive disorders arising during pregnancy, including preeclampsia, increases almost 3-fold. In pregnant women with adenomyosis, the incidence of labor abnormalities and postpartum complications significantly increases ($p<0.05$), mainly associated with increased blood loss (postpartum hemorrhage, hematometra).

Gestational complications, abnormalities of labor, and postpartum pathology in patients even with stage 1 of adenomyosis spread are largely related to the structural features of the endometrial-myometrial junctional zone. This is confirmed by data from other researchers who state that the development of adenomyosis is a consequence of the direct invasion of the endometrium into the myometrium. Consequently, in adenomyosis, regardless of its severity, the endometrium possesses an increased capacity for proliferation. These disturbances in the remodeling zone of the spiral arterioles likely lead to their abnormal transformation in the area of primary, secondary, and tertiary chorionic villi formation, defective differentiation of connective tissue structures and the vascular network, and untimely regressive processes in the epithelial lining of the placenta, which ultimately causes most of the aforementioned obstetric complications.

Conclusion. Thus, women with adenomyosis are characterized by an increased frequency of reproductive losses, as well as complications of gestation, labor, and the postpartum period. This emphasizes the necessity of detecting and timely correcting this pathology, even in its early stages, within the complex of pregravid preparation.